

DESIGN, FABRICATION, AND TESTING OF A LIGHT WEIGHT HYBRID CONCRETE FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER BRIDGE GIRDER

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ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) bridge systems have become popular amongst bridge engineers due to their lightweight and high durability. While FRP bridge systems possess many advantages over traditional bridge systems, linear behaviour followed by brittle failures and other failures such as delamination and plate buckling have hindered the uptake of the FRP bridge systems. High capacity reduction factors used in design have resulted in increased costs and embodied energy. This paper presents the development of a lightweight hybrid concrete-FRP bridge girder which is capable of providing nonlinear load-deformation behaviour and avoiding delamination and plate buckling failures.

KEYWORDS

Light weight bridge girder; Controlled failure; Finite Element Modelling; Composite Girder Design; Experimental testing

INTRODUCTION

The use of fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) in bridge construction is becoming increasingly popular amongst bridge engineers due to many advantages of FRPs, such as high specific strength, high corrosion resistance, ease of application, and lightweight (Alnahhal & Aref, 2008). Several FRP bridge technologies have been developed, including all FRP and hybrid concrete-FRP bridge systems (Deskovic et al., 1995; Gan et al., 1999; Karbhari & Seible, 2000; Correia et al., 2005; Bottenberg, 2010; Kulpa & Siwowski, 2019). FRP bridge decks were reported to weigh 20% less than a typical reinforced concrete (RC) deck (Mara et al. 2014). This weight savings can be utilised to increase overall load capacity without having to strengthen other support elements of the bridge. In addition, the ability to pre-fabricate minimises installation time and traffic disturbances.

While existing FRP bridge systems have shown great benefits compared to conventional RC, steel, and timber bridge systems, FRP bridge systems were shown to suffer from brittle failure modes, delamination and separation of flanges from the webs, and buckling of the FRP plate elements (Keller & Schollmayer, 2004; Camata & Shing, 2005; Canning et al., 2007; Morcoux et al., 2010; Neagoe et al., 2015). Due to the linear elastic mechanical response of FRPs, bridge systems manufactured using FRPs often exhibit almost linear behaviour until the ultimate load followed by brittle failures (Stone et al., 2001; Nordin & Täljsten, 2004; Keller et al., 2007; Vovesný & Rotter, 2012). Bridge engineers consider such brittle failures without much nonlinearity unsafe due to a lack of pre-warning before failure. As a result, significant reduction factors are applied in the design of FRP bridge systems, resulting in lower utilisation of the material strength. The bottom glass FRP (GFRP) strain of sandwich deck panels tested by Kupla & Siwowski (2019) reported less than 20% use of the GFRP strength. Such inefficient usage of materials results in high costs and increased embodied energy.

This paper presents the development of a lightweight hybrid concrete-FRP bridge girder (called "composite girder" hereafter for brevity), which can overcome the common issues experienced by existing FRP bridge systems. First, the design hypothesis of the composite girder is presented. Then the

conceptual design of a composite girder is presented. Based on the learning from the conceptual design study, the development of the final design of the composite girder is presented.

DESIGN HYPOTHESIS

In bridge engineering, early warnings typically related to plastic deformations are desired to ensure bridge inspectors can identify damage and arrange interventions before the failure of the bridge. Lack of such indications of damage increases the risk of failure. As a result, heavy capacity reduction factors are introduced for FRP bridge systems (which typically show linear behaviour until failure) to ensure required safety. If nonlinear load-deformation behaviour with clear indications of damage initiation and propagation could be achieved in FRP bridge systems, the damage could be detected before reaching failure with relative ease; thus risk of failure could be minimised without having to use high-capacity reduction factors. It was hypothesised that through the control of failure to be in steel shear keys between concrete and the FRP girders, nonlinear load-displacement behaviour of the composite girder could be achieved, leading to sufficient warning before final failure.

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN DEVELOPMENT OF THE BRIDGE GIRDER

The geometry of the bridge girder

Considering the bridge girders are subjected to significant flexural loads, a hollow section which increases the second moment of area, therefore, providing a higher flexural stiffness and strength while reducing the material volume (Boreasi et al., 1985) was selected as the girder geometry (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The cross-section of the proposed composite bridge girder (H -total height, w_c -width of the top flange, w_{cf} -width of the bottom flange h_c -thickness of concrete, h_w -height of the web, t_w -thickness of web, t_{GF} -thickness of GFRP, t_{CF} -thickness of CFRP)

Selection of materials for the bridge deck

The materials were selected based on knowledge from existing literature to maximise the capacity while keeping the embodied energy and cost low. Concrete was selected as the compression element of the girder system due to its high compressive strength-to-cost ratio and excellent performance as a wearing surface (Arel & Aydin, 2018). Carbon FRP (CFRP) was selected as the main tensile reinforcement due to its high strength-to-weight ratio and was placed at the bottom of the cross-section (i.e. at the tensile most fibre). Bi-directional GFRP (i.e. $\pm 45^\circ$), which is lower cost than CFRP, yet provide sufficient strength, was chosen for the webs as the main shear reinforcement. To ensure sufficient strength against web-flange separation failures (Keller & Schollmayer, 2004), GFRP was continued from the webs to the flange of the inner box section. This fibre continuity also provides tensile reinforcement in the width direction for concrete spanning between the webs. To avoid web buckling failures (Pham & Hancock, 2009), a cost-efficient timber core was sandwiched between the GFRP skins of the web. Steel shear keys were selected to transfer forces between concrete and the web.

Preliminary design methodology

The preliminary design capacity of the girder was evaluated based on the flexural and shear capacity of the cross-section. An optimisation of the cross-section parameters (as shown in Figure 1) was carried out to minimise the material volume while meeting the capacity requirements. In the calculation of the flexural capacity, a section analysis methodology was employed, assuming the girder behaves as an Euler Bernoulli beam, which ignored the shear slip between the concrete and the webs. To account for

potential errors due to this assumption, the compressive crushing strain was limited to 55% of the crushing strain of concrete. Concrete stress-strain behaviour was used as given in BS 8110-1 (1997) but with reduced ultimate strain. Linear elastic perfectly plastic behaviour was assumed for steel shear keys. The behaviours of the GFRP and CFRP were assumed to be linear elastic until failure. The limiting strain of the CFRP laminate was taken as the lower value of the rupture strain and the debonding strain. The debonding strain of the CFRP was calculated assuming debonding failure to occur within the adhesive interface. Fracture energy in mode II was calculated using the methodology provided by Fernando (2010) for CFRP-to-steel interfaces failing through cohesive failure within the adhesive.

The shear capacity of the bridge deck cross-section was evaluated considering only the GFRP on either side of the web stiffeners contributes towards resisting shear forces. Although, in reality, there is a shear contribution from the web stiffeners as well, it was ignored in the preliminary calculations.

Conventional shear key design methodologies for steel-concrete composite girders are done to avoid steel shear key failure until the girder's full flexural capacity is reached. Therefore, the conventional approach for the design of shear keys is of little use in the design of the proposed girder of this study. When designing the shear keys for the proposed composite girder, it is essential to ensure shear keys behave linear elastic until serviceability limit state loads are exceeded. It is also important to ensure failure initiation and propagation occur through steel shear keys to ensure nonlinear deformations before the ultimate load is reached. A preliminary finite element (FE) model was utilised to design the shear keys. Details of the FE model are not given here due to page limitations but can be found in Rathnayake (2023). Each component's dimensions were selected to ensure adequate elastic stiffness of the girder to keep the deflections lower than the required values.

In addition to the above-discussed main design criteria, further consideration was given to avoid punching failure in concrete (by providing adequate thickness of concrete and transverse GFRP reinforcement between webs), web buckling failure (by fabricating the webs with stiffer material to provide sufficient stiffness against lateral movements), and bearing failure in the concrete and the webs (by selecting adequate diameter for the steel shear keys).

Preliminary experimental study

In order to verify the research hypothesis and to verify the preliminary design methodology, three nominally identical small-scale composite girders were designed, manufactured, and tested under 3-point bending. The cross-section design was carried out to meet the ultimate capacity of a 100mm by 150mm RC cross-section beam (Figure 2b). Efforts were made to find the best parameters of the cross-section to minimise the material quantity while ensuring the required section capacity is met. The dimensions of the composite girder cross section determined through the above process is shown in Figure 2a. In total 4 layers of ± 45 bi-directional glass fibre (GF) fabric, (2 layers on either side of plywood) of 650 gsm were used for webs, top flange and the bottom flange. A 1.2mm thick uni-directional CFRP pultruded laminate was bonded to the bottom flange. The Span of the beam was taken to be 2m.

Figure 2: The cross sections of (a) small-scale composite girder (b) RC girder

All the girders were tested under four-point bending using a 100kN capacity Tecnotest machine. The support span was set to 1800mm, and loading was applied symmetrically with a 600mm distance between the two loading points in displacement control mode at a displacement rate of 1mm/min.

Preliminary experimental study results and discussion

Table 1 shows the test results of the tested RC girder and the three composite girders. CN refers to the RC girder, while CM 1, CM 2 and CM 3 refer to the three composite girders. The CN girder reached an ultimate load of 62.14kN at a mid-span displacement of 51.7mm, while the composite girders CM 1, CM 2 and CM 3 reached an ultimate load of 53.22kN, 53.31kN and 56kN, respectively, with mid-span displacements 53.22mm, 53.31mm, and 56.00 mm respectively.

Table 1: Test results of the tested RC and the composite girders.

Beam	Ultimate load (kN)	Mid-span displacement (mm)	Average CFRP strain	CFRP utilisation (%)	Load/Weight ratio
CN	62.14	51.7	-	-	0.86
CM 1	53.22	40.4	0.00652	35.80	2.47
CM 2	53.31	41.3	0.00595	32.69	2.48
CM 3	56.00	56.7	0.00846	46.46	2.60

The load-displacement curves of the three composite girders and the RC girder are compared in Figure 3a. All three composite girders achieved ultimate load capacities closer to the RC girder's. The ultimate deformation of the composite girders was also similar to the RC girder. All three composite girders showed nonlinear behaviour. However, the composite girders' initial stiffness was lower than the RC girder. Failed composite girders are shown in Figures 3b-d. All the composite girders failed due to the shearing of the steel shear keys and then splitting the concrete due to the crack underneath the loading point. At the final stages (soon after the ultimate load is reached), some bearing failures of the webs could also be seen.

(a) Load-displacement curves

(b) Failed girder CM 1

(c) Failed girder CM 2

(d) Failed girder CM 3

Figure 3: Load-displacement curves of all the tested girders (i.e. Reinforced concrete (CN) and composite (CM) girders) and the failed composite girders (i.e. CM 1, CM 2, and CM 3)

All the composite girders showed nonlinear load-displacement behaviour, and the failure was initiated due to shear key failures. From the test observations, it was clear that nonlinear load-displacement

behaviour can be achieved by controlling the failure at steel shear keys. Therefore, the small-scale tests conducted in this study verified the research hypothesis that "nonlinear load-displacement behaviour can be achieved through controlling the failure to initiate and propagate at the shear keys". Initial stiffness of the composite girders was lower than that calculated from the design methodology (assuming perfect composite action between the constituents). Therefore, improvement to the preliminary design methodology was found to be necessary for better design of the composite girders.

A complete fracture of the shear keys was observed in the small-scale composite girders. As standard steel shear keys are not available in the diameters required for small composite girders, steel screws were used as the shear keys. Such steel screws show lower deformation capacity than conventional mild-steel shear keys. Use of shear keys with high deformation capacity could further improve the load and deformation capacities of the composite girders. Web stiffeners were found to provide sufficient resistance against buckling failures. However, due to the inclined angle of the web, localised rupture of the GFRP and bearing failure of the webs could be observed. The use of straight webs could avoid such issues.

CFRP laminate showed no debonding, and axial strains of the CFRP laminate (obtained from the strain gauges placed at the mid-span of the specimens) showed closer to 50% utilisation of the CFRP laminate tensile strength. The weight of the RC girder was 72.25 kg, while the weight of the composite girders varied between 21.49 kg-21.55kg. Weight specific load capacity of the RC girder was 0.86 kN/kg, while for girders CN 1, CN 2, and CN 3 it was 2.47 kN/kg, 2.48 kN/kg, and 2.60 kN/kg, respectively. This shows composite girders can provide significantly lighter solutions with higher weight-specific load capacity than RC girders.

FINAL DESIGN OF THE COMPOSITE GIRDER

Revised composite girder cross section

Based on the learnings from the small-scale composite girder tests, several improvements to the cross-section of the conceptual design were made: (a) inclined web design was found to result in movement of the webs in the lateral direction leading to failures such as rupture of the GFRP and bearing failures. Therefore, webs without any inclination were used in the new design; (b) shear key positions were moved to align with the vertical webs, and the web stiffeners were used as the bearing surface for the steel shear key force transfer; (c) as the utilisation of the CFRP laminates were found to be only 50%, CFRP laminates were provided only at the bottom of the web region, instead of along the full width of the bottom flange; (d) while timber was used as web stiffeners in the small scale composite girders, increase in load demand on shear keys may lead to failure in timber. Therefore an alternative material option was considered for web stiffeners. Comparing different options, chopped waste GF-reinforced epoxy filler was chosen as the web stiffener. Using waste GFs provides a pathway towards recycling fibre composites, thus allowing carbon storage. The final cross-section of the composite girder is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Final design of the composite girder cross section

Improved design methodology

The preliminary design of the composite girder was done using simplified analytical models and a preliminary FE model. However, test results showed that improvements are necessary to the design methodology for better accuracy. It was clear that failure control at the shear keys also the mean

assumption of perfect composite sections (i.e. negligible slip at the concrete-web interface) was not accurate. A more sophisticated approach capable of capturing the complex behaviours of different components and their interactions within the composite girder was necessary for accurate design. Therefore, an FE model using commercially available FE software ABAQUS (2021) was developed to capture the composite girder's behaviour accurately.

Different components of the FE model are given in Figure 5. GFRP laminates were modelled using 4-node shell elements with reduced integration (S4R) (Figure 5a). CFRP laminate was modelled as a shell using S4R elements (Figure 5b). Web stiffener was modelled as a solid geometry using 8-node solid elements (C3D8R) (Figure 5c). GFRP web surface nodes were tied with the respective web stiffener surface nodes assuming no interfacial slip between them. CFRP laminate surface nodes were tied to the respective GFRP and web surface nodes, assuming no debonding/slip between them.

Figure 5: Different components of the FE model (a) GFRP laminates (b) CFRP laminate (c) Web – Epoxy mixed with GF chopped strands (d) Shear keys – Steel bolts (e) Steel wire mesh (f) Concrete

Steel shear keys were modelled using the exact solid geometry (Figure 5d). However, in modelling the steel shear keys, geometry along the height was divided into three regions, namely: (a) embedded region within the web stiffener; (b) a unit thickness cohesive layer right above the top surface of the web; and (c) embedded region within the concrete. Embedded regions within the web stiffener and concrete were modelled as solid embedded elements, while the unit thickness region was modelled using cohesive elements (COH3D8). Embedded elements assumed no failure within steel shear keys and web stiffeners or concrete. It was assumed that the cohesive region within the embedded regions will capture the overall load-shear displacement behaviour of the steel shear key-concrete-web stiffener system.

The concrete layer was modelled using 8-node solid elements (C3D8R). Contact behaviour was defined between top surface of the GFRP and web stiffeners and the underside of the concrete to avoid penetration of the surfaces in to each other. Contact was defined using hard contact for normal behaviour, but with separation allowed in tension, and shear behaviour was assumed to be frictionless.

To find out the tensile and shear material properties of GFRP, a laminate with three layers of 350 gsm $\pm 45^\circ$ bi-directional GF fabric and Ampreg 31 epoxy was fabricated and cut to specific tensile and shear coupon dimensions and tested as per ASTM D3039 (2008) and ASTM D7078 (2000). The fibre orientation of tensile and shear coupons was set to $\pm 45^\circ$ from the coupon axis. Instead of using the composite layup option in ABAQUS (2021), bi-directional laminate was modelled as a single layer using the experimentally obtained properties from the GFRP coupons. Details of the coupon tests are given in Rathnayake (2023). Average elastic constants in parallel (i.e. direction 1) and perpendicular (i.e. direction 2) to the girder axis were found to be: $E_1=E_2=5.6$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{21}=0.49$, and $G_{12}=G_{21}=5.2$ GPa respectively. Only elastic behaviour was considered, and maximum strength criteria were used for damage modelling.

The CFRP laminate used was a 1.2 mm thick pultruded laminate. Elastic constants in parallel and perpendicular to girder axis directions E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} , ν_{21} , and G_{12} were obtained through experiments to be 103.94 GPa, 6.62 GPa, 0.25, 0.02, and 4.88 GPa, respectively. Linear elastic behaviour was assumed until ultimate strength (2400 MPa in fibre direction) followed by brittle fracture.

The material behaviour of the web stiffeners was considered isotropic. Tensile and shear coupon tests were carried out for the chopped GF strand-epoxy webs. The tensile elastic modulus was found to be 5.61 GPa; the shear modulus was found to be 2.10 GPa. The Poisson's ratio was taken as 0.27. Tensile strength and shear strength were found to be 35.67 MPa and 36.54 MPa, respectively. Linear elastic behaviour was assumed until failure. Failure was assumed to occur when stress reached the maximum strength values (tensile strength was taken to be equal to compressive strength).

The concrete damage plasticity model available in ABAQUS (2021) was used to model the damage behaviour of concrete. 28-day compressive strength of concrete was found to be 70MPa through cylinder tests. The stress-crack opening displacement relationship given by Hordijk (1993) defined the behaviour under tension. CEB-FIP (1991) model was used to calculate the tensile strength and the fracture energy of concrete. More details of the model are given in Rathnayake (2023).

The behaviour of the interface between concrete and girder web connected through the steel shear keys was modelled using a traction separation model. Interface behaviour until failure initiation was assumed to be linearly elastic. Normal stiffness was taken as the axial stiffness of the steel shear keys. Stiffness in mode II was estimated from the experiments of shear pull-off tests of the GF strand-epoxy to concrete specimens. Specimens dimensions, test set-up, and the force-slip results are given in Figure 6, while details of the experiments are given in Rathnayake (2023).

Figure 6: Shear key pull-off test specimens and results: (a) dimensions of the specimens, (b) test set-up, (c) Force-slip behaviour.

Experimentally obtained mode II traction-separation behaviour (i.e. force-slip behaviour) of the steel shear keys was idealised to be a tri-linear curve (Figure 7) and given by :

$$\tau = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_{max}\delta_1}{\delta} & \text{if } \delta \leq \delta_1 \\ \tau_{max} - \frac{(\tau_{max}-\tau_2)(\delta_2-\delta)}{\delta_2-\delta_1} & \text{if } \delta_1 < \delta \leq \delta_2 \\ \tau_2 - \frac{\tau_2(\delta_f-\delta)}{\delta_f-\delta_2} & \text{if } \delta_2 < \delta < \delta_f \\ 0 & \text{if } \delta_f \leq \delta \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where τ is the mode II stress, τ_{max} is the mode II maximum strength, τ_2 is the mode II stress at the change in softening gradient (Figure 7), δ is the shear slip, δ_1 is the shear slip at bond strength, δ_2 is the slip at the gradient changing point of the softening branch (Figure 7), and δ_f is the slip at complete

failure. Based on the experimental results, following values were defined for the above force-slip parameters: $\tau_{max} = 168 \text{ MPa}$; $\tau_2 = 115 \text{ MPa}$; $\delta_1 = 3 \text{ mm}$; $\delta_2 = 40 \text{ mm}$; and $\delta_f = 45 \text{ mm}$. From the area under the force-slip curve, critical fracture work per unit area G_{II} is estimated to be 5775 N/mm .

Figure 7: Idealised tri-linear traction-separation model for mode II behaviour

No damage was assumed to occur under mode I, while damage under mode II was assumed to occur when the following criterion is met:

$$\frac{\sqrt{t_s^2 + t_t^2}}{\tau_{max}} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where, τ_{max} is the traction at the failure initiation, t_s and t_t are the shear traction in s and t coordinate directions. Once the damage initiates, a scalar damage variable D is introduced where shear tractions are related to shear slips (δ_s, δ_t) as $t_i = (1 - D)\delta_i \forall i \in (s, t)$. D is equal to zero at the initiation of damage and is equal to one at the complete failure of the interface. The complete failure of the interface is defined based on fracture energy considerations. Full damage is expected to occur when:

$$\frac{G_{s,t}}{G_{II}} = 1 \quad (3)$$

where $G_{s,t}$ is the combined work done by the tractions and their conjugate displacements in the two shear directions per unit area. To describe the evolution of damage, the definition of an effective displacement is introduced as follows:

$$\delta_m = \sqrt{\delta_s^2 + \delta_t^2} \quad (4)$$

Based on the idealised tri-linear model shown in Figure 7, the damage variable D is then defined by the following equation:

$$D = \begin{cases} \frac{(\delta_2 - \frac{\tau_2}{K_{SS}})(\delta_m - \delta_1)}{\delta_m(\delta_2 - \delta_1)} & \text{if } \delta_m \leq \delta_2 \\ 1 - \frac{\tau_2(\delta_f - \delta_m)}{K_{SS}\delta_m(\delta_f - \delta_2)} & \text{if } \delta_f \geq \delta_m > \delta_2 \\ 1 & \text{if } \delta_m > \delta_f \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Embedded regions of the steel shear keys were modelled using isotropic material properties. As nonlinear interface behaviours (including shear key) are captured through interface behaviour, only linear elastic material properties for steel were used. Elastic modulus was assumed to be 200 GPa .

Simply supported boundary conditions were applied on the bottom flange of the I-girder on nodes intersecting a line 100 mm from the girder ends. The loading was applied to the girder through the displacement of a steel roller (Figure 5f). The roller surface was modelled to be in hard contact with the

top surface of the concrete. A dynamic implicit method with quasi-static energy dissipation was adopted for the analysis. The mesh sizes of the different components were selected based on the interactions between them. Concrete meshed to 20 mm element sizes. Nevertheless, the edges along the thickness of concrete meshed to have at least 10 elements. The web stiffener and the GFRP laminates on either side of the web also meshed to 20 mm, while the steel shear key with a cohesive zone meshed to 5 mm. The bottom CFRP laminate meshed to a 20 mm element size.

Fabrication of the medium scale composite girder

In the medium-scale composite girder fabrication, polystyrene foam was used as a stay-in-place mould. Due to the polystyrene foam's low elastic modulus and strength, no contribution from it is expected to the structural performance of the composite girder. In fabricating the composite girder, the polystyrene foam core was cut to the required dimensions. Then, three layers of 600 gsm $\pm 45^\circ$ bi-directional GF woven fabric (cut to 700 mm by 2 m segments) were well saturated with Tyfo S epoxy adhesive and bonded onto the three sides of the polystyrene foam core, as shown in Figure 8a. The layers were bonded onto the foam core one after the other while applying sufficient pressure from the rollers to avoid wrinkles and expel the entrapped air.

Figure 8: Fabricated medium-scale composite girder before casting concrete

A 1.2 mm thick and 100 mm wide uni-directional pultruded CFRP laminate was cut to a length of 2m, and the bonding surface was sanded to remove any oxide layer and was well cleaned with acetone to get a dust and dirt-free bonding surface. The two polystyrene cores with bonded GFRP were kept on a table 30 mm apart (web thickness), and then, the CFRP laminate with epoxy applied on the bonding surface was placed on the gap as shown in Figure 8b. The two bottom ends of the girder (i.e. right on top of the support locations) were further stiffened with two layers of 0/90 bi-directional GFRP to avoid punching failures at the supports (Figure 8b). This also prevents the CFRP laminate from debonding at the supports (which is only a problem expected in girders with short spans). Then several weights were kept on top of the CFRP laminate to apply pressure, and the girder was left to cure for 72 hours before removing the weights.

Figure 9: Medium-scale composite beam; (a) Installed shear keys; (b) Formwork for concreting; (c) Steel wire mesh; and (d) Concreting

Next, the whole set-up with the two polystyrene cores with GFRP and the bottom CFRP laminate was flipped to the upright position as shown in Figure 9a and the two open ends of the web spacing were properly sealed to prevent the epoxy from leaking out when the webs are filled with chopped GF strands mixed with epoxy. Then, chopped GF strands (approx. 6mm length) were mixed with Tyfo S epoxy to

the volume proportion 1:1.5 and poured into the web spacing to fill the gap. After filling the web spacing with the mix, steel bolts of 7mm diameter were placed in the web, as shown in Figure 9a, at a spacing of 50mm. The steel bolts are 180mm long and placed inside the web, leaving 15mm out to connect with the top concrete. This was allowed to cure for another 48 hours, and after the web was fully cured, a formwork was manufactured with plywood around the composite beam as shown in Figure 9b for casting concrete. Before concreting, a steel wire mesh was placed in the formwork as shown in Figure 9c. The wire mesh reinforces the concrete and supports concrete to carry the tensile stresses while holding the concrete together when the concrete is cracked. Finally, concrete was poured onto the girder, as shown in Figure 9d.

Testing of the medium scale composite girder

The medium-scale composite girder was tested under 3-point bending with simply supported conditions at a support span of 1800 mm. Three displacement transducers (SP 1, SP 2, SP 3) were mounted on the bottom of the beam at mid-span and 450 mm on either side of the mid-span to measure the vertical deflection of the girder. The axial strain of the CFRP laminate was measured at three locations SG 1, SG 2, and SG 3 at mid-span and 200 mm on either side of the mid-span, respectively. Testing was carried out using a 1 MN MTS universal testing machine at a 1mm/min displacement rate.

Results and discussions

Figure 10a shows the failed specimen, and the final failure was observed to be the compression crushing of concrete at the loading point. During the loading, the concrete top flange was found to bend in the transverse direction, and a tensile crack appeared along the girder's mid-width (Figure 10b). However, the appearance of the crack did not create any apparent change in the load-displacement behaviour. Some bearing/rupture failures on the top GFRP flange right beneath failed concrete were also seen (Figure 10c). However, whether this has occurred during the process of concrete failure or at the end with a sudden movement of concrete at mid-span due to brittle failure is unclear.

Figure 10: Failures of the composite girder showing concrete crushing, transverse tensile cracks in concrete, bearing/rupture of GFRP top flange, and interfacial shear slip at the end of the girder

During the testing, a slip between the concrete and web interface could also be observed (Figure 10d). During the testing, cracking of the polystyrene foam could be observed due to the high curvature of the girder. Once the test was completed, the polystyrene foam was removed, and the inner web was inspected. No delamination or web buckling could be seen, thus confirming the adequacy of the design. Inspection of the bottom CFRP laminate showed no signs of failure, thus also confirming the adequacy of the design. The experimental load-mid span deflection curve is given in Figure 11 and compared with the FE results. The experimental curve showed an excellent agreement with the FE results, confirming the FE modelling approach's ability to predict the composite girders' behaviour accurately. The load-mid span deflection behaviour was significantly nonlinear, confirming the accuracy of the design. The interfacial slip was observed during the loading, which also confirmed the failure initiation within the concrete-web interface.

The Medium-scale girder design was found to overcome the shortcomings observed in the small-scale girder and thus was deemed successful. FE-based design methodology accurately captured the behaviour of the composite girder. Failure was initiated in steel shear keys, but steel shear keys managed

to keep transferring the load without fracture until the concrete failure. Debonding failures and web buckling failures were successfully avoided in the current design. From the strain readings of the CFRP laminate, it was found that the CFRP utilisation was increased to approx. 60% of the strength. Considering the high material safety factor typically used for CFRP in designs, 60% utilisation of the CFRP strength is reasonably high. Considering all the above, the design can be considered as successful.

Figure 11: Comparison of experimental and FE load vs mid-span displacement curves of the medium-scale composite girder

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the development of a hybrid concrete-FRP girder (composite girder). It was hypothesised that nonlinear load-displacement behaviour could be obtained through control of the failures to be in steel shear keys. At first, small-scale composite girders were designed, manufactured and tested. Experimental results showed a failure to be in steel shear keys, and load-displacement behaviour was found to be nonlinear. Therefore, small-scale tests verified the design hypothesis. Based on the observations made on small-scale girder tests, further improvements were made to the cross-section design of the composite girder and the design methodology.

A detailed FE model was developed to capture the composite girder's behaviour accurately. The cohesive zone modelling approach was used to capture the behaviour of the concrete-web stiffener interface connection (connected via steel shear keys). Traction-separation behaviour of the concrete-web stiffener interface was obtained through single-shear pull-off tests. Experimental traction-separation behaviour was implemented in the FE model by using an idealised tri-linear model. Based on the results of the FE model, a medium-scale composite girder was designed and tested under 3-point bending. From the current study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Through control of the failure in steel shear keys, it was possible to obtain the nonlinear load-displacement behaviour of the composite girders. This allows pre-warnings before failure, thus can lead to minimising the risk of failure.
- The composite girder's design was able to successfully avoid failures such as delamination/debonding and FRP plate buckling.
- The design of the composite girder presented was able to utilise 60% of the CFRP laminate strength, therefore, shown to be efficient in terms of material utilisation.
- The composite girder was found to result in high weight-specific strength compared to RC girders.
- The proposed FE approach was found to capture the behaviour of the composite girder accurately and thus can be used as a tool for designing composite girders.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is found in its entirety in Rathnayake (2023).

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